

**COLOR SYMBOLISM IN AMERICAN AND UZBEK FANTASTIC
WORKS. (EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF RAY BRADBURY, IZAEK
ASIMOV, KHOJIAKBAR SHAIKHOV AND ISAJAN SULTON)**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8198883>

ABSTRACT: This article discusses color symbolism in American and Uzbek fantasy works. It provides information about the use of colors, their significance, their different aspects and importance in different nations, as shown in the works of Ray Bradbury, Isaac Asimov, Khojiakbar ShaikhoV and Isajon Sultan.

KEY WORDS: symbolism, fiction, symbolic details, genre, spiritual experience

INTRODUCTION

The concept of “fantasy” is derived from the Greek language and means “the art of imagination”. In fact, fiction is only an imagination created by the power of the mind and does not exist in real life. Although this genre is a product of the world of fantasy, traces of real reality can be felt in it. Because the world of fantasy takes power from this reality and takes flight. Fantasy and creativity are closely related and go hand in hand.

The writer uses colors in order to convey the emotions of the work and the psyche of the characters to the reader. But the meaning of each color can have a different meaning in each nation. If we explain with the example of black color, black is a sign of evil, ugliness, and evil according to Western culture, but in the Muslim world, black acquires a positive meaning due to the black color of the Kaaba, which is sacred to Muslims.

MAIN PART

The above-mentioned writers used the gloss of colors very skillfully in their works. First, if we look at the example of Isaac Asimov's work, we can see that colors are used in their place.

- *“The other man stood up. It was obvious to him that his decision had come none too soon. He walked slowly about the long table, toward the Earthman.*

He said soothingly, “It will be for your own good.” He took the black rod from his pocket.”¹

¹ Isaac Asimov The Currents of Space 1956 –P 5

- *"The interlocutor stood up. He went around the big table and began to approach the Earthling. His words were too polite. "I am only looking for your benefit. "A black sturgeon appeared in his hand."²*

As I said above, the meaning of black color is different depending on the traditions of different nations. But in many places, black is used in negative terms, to express depression.

Ray Bradbury, one of the greatest American fantasy writers of the 20th century, became famous worldwide after the publication of his dystopian novel "Fahrenheit 451". After that, each new book of the writer became a big reality. We can see that the writer used the image of colors beautifully and skillfully in his works.

"If it rubs off, it means I'm in love. Has it?"

He could hardly do anything else but look.

"Well?" she said.

*"You're **yellow** under there."*

"Fine! Let's try YOU now."

"It won't work for me."

"Here." Before he could move she had put the dandelion under his chin. He drew back and she laughed. "Hold still!"

She peered under his chin and frowned.

"Well?" he said.

"What a shame," she said. "You're not in love with anyone."³

In this extract yellow symbolized happiness in life. Bradbury wanted to indicate in Montag's life has no happiness and meaning before meeting Clarissa.

Once as a child he had sat upon a *yellow dune* by the sea in the middle of the *blue and hot summer* day, trying to fill a sieve with sand, because some cruel cousin had said, "Fill this sieve and you'll get a dime!" And the faster he poured, the faster it sifted through with a hot whispering. His hands were tired, the sand was boiling, and the sieve was empty. Seated there in the midst of July, without a sound, he felt the tears move down his cheeks.⁴

As Montag rides the subway on his way to see Faber, he recalls a trick that his cousin played on him by trying to get him to fill a sieve with sand, knowing that the sand would fall through the open spaces. As a child, Montag could see that no matter how hard he tried, no matter how fast he worked, the sieve wouldn't fill with sand, and yet he kept trying. Montag's childhood memory

² Ayzek Azimov Koinot oqimlari. –T.: Davr Press NMU, 2017. –B 10

³ Ray Bradbury, Fahrenheit 451. New York: Simon & Schuster Paperbacks. (1995). 10- b.

⁴ Ray Bradbury, Fahrenheit 451. New York: Simon & Schuster Paperbacks. (1995). 36-b.

symbolizes his present situation: Despite his efforts, Montag feels that same frustration when trying to understand the truths of life.

- *"Trantor! It was always first in his thought, yet he was not the kind of fool who would worship a cluster of stars or the yellow emblem of Spaceship-and- Sun that the Trantorian armed forces wore. In short, he was not a patriot in the ordinary meaning of the word and Trantor as Trantor meant nothing to him."*⁵

*"Trantor! He was always at the forefront of the ambassador's thoughts, but Able was no fool to divine the starry heavens or the yellow insignia of the Trantorian military with suns and spaceships."*⁶

It is no wonder that the first thing that comes to everyone's mind when they think of yellow is the sun. That's why yellow color means energy, strength, power. But yellow also has different meanings in different cultures. For example: among the people of Brazil, yellow color means intelligence and wealth. In India it is a symbol of luck, in Japan it is a symbol of courage, in Egypt it is a symbol of happiness, and it is also a symbol of mourning, while for the Greek people it means bad luck and bad luck, and for Mexicans it is the color of mourning. For Muslim nations, yellow symbolizes wisdom, wisdom, and justice.

-*"The reality was pleasant enough. In Florina's mild climate, it was green all year round. It had its patches of lawn, wooded areas and stony grottoes. It had a little pool with decorative fish in it and a larger pool for children to paddle in"*⁷

-*"Due to the moderate climate of Florina, the park was always green. There were meadows, groves of trees, caves cut into the rocks, and a small pool with goldfish swimming in it, and a larger pool for children to swim in."*⁸

This genre was developed in world literature in the middle of the 20th century, but it entered Uzbek literature a little late in the late 1960s. Now fiction has formed as an independent genre with its own characteristics in our literature. Azod Sharofiddinov describes the writer as follows: "If we call this initial period the spring of fiction, Hojiakbar Shaykhov is considered the swallow of this trend."

When spring comes, everything turns green. It is no exaggeration to say that the spring season itself is the season of renewal and living, and its symbolic color green. Green color represents growth, new life, renewal. But even so, at the

⁵ Isaac Asimov The Currents of Space 1956 –P 54

⁶ Ayzek Azimov Koinot oqimlari. –T.: Davr Press NMU, 2017. –B 61

⁷ Isaac Asimov The Currents of Space 1956 –P 91

⁸ Ayzek Azimov Koinot oqimlari. –T.: Davr Press NMU, 2017. –B 95

intersection of cultural points, green has different meanings. For example, for the people of England and Ireland, green means magic and lies.

*-When the girls hurriedly crossed the threshold of the four-story school gate, Nazira - the fourth, Nargiza - the third, and Nafisa - the second floor, when the red "Toyota" suddenly stopped at the school gate."*⁹

Along with expressing feelings such as love, desire, and loyalty, which are most necessary for a person, red also means anger, anger, war, and danger in a person. In a word, red is the color of life, the color of the blood flowing in our veins. Because red color is dark, it can cause a little anxiety.

*-“After a few more moments, they formed a circle around the white sofa and started talking.”*¹⁰

White is a symbol of purity, peace and happiness. In many works depicting fighting, they show a white flag in order to show that they are not going to fight, but have surrendered. Brides also wear white dresses on their wedding day to show that their intentions and hearts are white. But among Indians, white is the color of mourning. At the same time, when Muslims die, the shroud used to wrap the corpse is also white. For this reason, we cannot say that any color has a specific meaning. Each nation expresses different meanings based on its culture, history, origin, religion, and politics.

*-“On the left side of the arch-shaped one-story windows, there is a door with carved flowers...”*¹¹

Air color is a light color and is a symbol of peace. If we relate it to psychology, it is possible to know that havarang is a sign of truth, it means reliability.

While analyzing the works written by the writers of the two continents, we saw that Western and Eastern cultures intersect at some points and contradict each other at other points. We have seen that some customs that seem normal for Western culture may not be true for Eastern culture at all, or vice versa.

In I.Sultan's work "Ozod", you can see the characteristics of specific meanings of symbolic details and symbolic signs. In the play, when Azad finally reached the tulip, he saw that it was black, unlike other tulips. Considering that the black color is a sign of strength and majesty, the color of the tulip may be a sign of its high status, and the fact that it is not similar to other tulips may have raised its level even more. Maybe he was born black because of lightning? There

⁹ Shayxov H. Tutash olamlar, Ikki jahon ovorasi . – T.: Sharq, 2001. –B 58

¹⁰ Shayxov H. Tutash olamlar, Ikki jahon ovorasi . – T.: Sharq, 2001. –B 73

¹¹ Shayxov H. Tutash olamlar, Ikki jahon ovorasi . – T.: Sharq, 2001. –B 11

are traces of lightning burns on the surface of this flower, whose opening is the service of lightning. On the other hand, he was sad:

"I don't know," said Lola, bowing her head. Then Azad saw that the tulip was sad and sad, tears like drops were shaking in its delicate petals"¹².

If we think about it, the conclusion that black is used here to express sadness is closer to the truth. The tulips sparkled and lit up, but her life was full of darkness, she didn't even know why it sprouted and why it was so precious.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the works of fiction by Ray Bradbury, Isaac Asimov, Khojiakbar Shaikhov and Isajon Sultan made a significant contribution not only to the development of science fiction, but also to the development of world and Uzbek literature. Their creative heritage deserves comprehensive study and research. The educational value of the writers' works is high, and they make the reader think deeply. Through the symbolism of a single color, the reader can develop the worldview, educate in the spirit of noble values, self-awareness, follow the right path in life, be conscientious, have faith, be kind and compassionate to people. builds openness and encourages broad thinking.

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